

ANALYSIS OF GENDER GAP IN STEM EDUCATION AND ITS REASONS IN INDIAN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

STEM education is very essential for the sustainable development of Nation. Although women constitute half of population but representation of girls in STEM education and women in STEM professionals is quite low, the problem is not only a case of India but it is global issues. STEM education has tagged as masculine in most of societies and this notion is ubiquitous in Indian culture. It has also observed that gender gap in STEM also intersect with other social variable of caste and class. The present paper is an attempt to analyse gender gap in STEM education and its probable reasons in Indian context. Analyses of authentic data from government of India also reveal a wide gap in STEM education especially in mathematics and engineering. This issue may pose a hurdle for sustainable development of nation in present IT age. Therefore, it is call of time that to pay concern on this issues and efforts should be made to bridge the gender gap in STEM education without any kind of discrimination.

KEYWORDS: Gender gap; STEM education; Stereotype

INTRODUCTION

In the present age where, the world around us shaped by science and technology, therefore, STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) education builds the premises for the Nation development. We enormously use the process or product of science in our day-to-day life. Hill et al., (2010) observed that STEM is critical for the National economy. STEM education and related professions are standard indicators for development of the Nation. The UNESCO Agenda 2030 also highlights that STEM is important for sustainable development and it can provide learners with the knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviours required for inclusive and sustainable societies (UNESCO, 2017). This agenda focused that low enrolment of girls in the school and their lower participation and achievement in STEM education is the major issue of concern for many of the countries. The agenda clearly mentioned that leaving of girls and women in STEM education and careers is a loss for all. Researches evident that schoolchildren to university level students perceived that mathematics, physics and chemistry are male dominated masculine subjects and are associated with attributes of complex, hard and thinking based subjects (Weinreich – Haste, 1981; Archer et al., 2010 and Cvencek et al. 2011). These gendered based notions about STEM education is prevail in most of the societies across the world. This gender segregation

is also reflects in the vocational orientation of adolescents that has been well documented for decades in most OECD countries (OECD, 2006, 2012). The STEM disciplines have been considered as masculine, as result gender gap is created and men are underrepresented in the fields of education, health and welfare whereas women representation is less in the STEM fields (WEF, 2017). Blackburn, (2017) studied on the status of women in STEM in last ten years from 2007-2017 and revealed that women are motivated now than the earlier past to pursue their career in STEM field. However, still they confronted with the barriers of stereotype, biases, chilly campus cultures, unsteady identities, and a wavering sense of belonging that hindered their successful degree completion and career entry. Besides, these women faculty also reported a collective lack of mentoring and supportive policies (particularly for work–life balance) leading to burnout. Thus, we have observed that even in the year the gender gap in STEM has reducing but still women facing challenges and difficulties in the STEM field and these challenges may be more difficult for developing country like us. In India the census, 2011 shows that, 82.2% of male and 65.5% of the female population of India are literate, this gender gap observed at each level of education and it is very vivid in reference to STEM education. Although the women comprises about half of the total population in India and due emphasis is given to participation of women, for true inclusive growth rate. However, the data related to progress in education in different fields reveal the existence of gender gap in the subjects' choices at higher education. Various reports developed by authentic organization of government of India reveals data that show the gender gap in STEM education.

GENDER GAP IN EDUCATION IN INDIAN SOCIETY: OVERALL VIEW

After independence, the literacy rate of female has been improves a lot but still there is 17% point gap exist in male and female literacy rate. Table-1 summarizes the literacy rate of male and female in different census report:

Table. 1 – Literacy Rate in India (in %) after independence

Census Year	Total Literacy	Male Literacy	Female Literacy	Gender Gap in Literacy Rae
1951	18.33	27.16	8.36	18.30
1961	28.30	40.40	15.35	25.05
1971	34.45	45.96	21.97	23.98
1981	43.57	56.83	29.76	26.62
1991	52.21	64.13	39.39	24.74
2001	64.80	75.30	53.70	21.60
2011	74.04	82.14	65.46	16.68

(Data Source: Census report, Government of India, 2013)

The data represented in the above table reveals that the gender gap in education has reduced over year but still it is a vast. Still there is significant gender gap in education. analysed the statistics of gender gap in higher education.

This gender gap in Indian society is quite more complex. Under article 15 of the Indian Constitution guarantees and ensures that the state shall not discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, and place of birth or any of them. The National Policy on Education, 1986 lay special emphasis on women's education. National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) also emphasize on equity and gender issues' in Science education in India.

Gender gap in education became deeper when we focus our attention towards gender gap in various disciplines. As Indian Science Report (2005) rightly remarked, "The health of nation

depends on, among other factors, the health of state of its Science and Technology” (Shukla, 2005). The significant of STEM education and its related professions is much more imperative for growing economy of developing country like India. Therefore, we cannot ignore our half population just because of their gender and the issues related to gender gap in education. While women play an important role in the contemporary society and contribute greatly for its development, their under representation in the sphere of Science and Technology is unfortunate.

In the developing countries like India, problem of gender inequality and lack of professional opportunities for women in STEM education is a challenging issue. The persistent gender gap in STEM could become more apparent when we see the subject wise enrolment of female in past ten years data of different time series as reported in Annual Reports of MHRD (2007-08, 2008-09, 2009-10, 2010-11, 2012-13) in table -3 .

Table -3. Year wise Enrolment of Female students in different discipline

Discipline	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2012-13
Arts	50.99	49.08	45.66	41.21	42.66 4
Science	20.18	19.99	19.98	19.14	19.07
Education	1.85	3.20	3.70	4.60	4.78
Engineering / Technology	4.17	4.90	7.69	11.36	10.55
Medicine	3.65	3.69	3.86	4.68	4.20
Agriculture	0.24	0.27	0.27	0.36	0.30
Veterinary Science	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.09

(Data Source: MHRD Annual Report, 2007-08, 2008-09, 2009-10, 2010-11, 2012-13)

The analysis of data reveals that from year 2007 the percentage of girl’s enrolled for graduation degree was 50.99 which was decreases to 42.66 in arts stream, since than more than 40 % of girls choose Bachelor of Arts that include humanities, social sciences and languages etc. However, female enrolment in Science stream shows slightly decreasing trend. In Engineering and Technology an increase in the enrolment up to the year 2010-11 could seen, however a slight decrease is also seen in the year 2013. Analysis of above data show good representation of women in arts and humanities and 28.3% (year 2007-08), 28.93% (year 2008-09), 31.87% (year 2009-10), 35.64% (year 2010-11), 34.21% (year 2012-13) women were enrolled in STEM field which is low as compare to arts and humanities also, shows that percentage of enrolment of women in Engineering and Technology is quite low. These enrolment figures clearly show the less participation of women in STEM field. It is also notable that data of science include good representation from home science and data of medicine have over representation female students in nursing. These home science and nursing are considered as conventional field for women only.

Past years data from year 2011 -2020 representing female per 100 male in different programmes of STEM and Arts and humanities are shown in following table give us a glance for gender gap in STEM education in Indian context.

Female per 100 male students in different major UG & PG programmes of STEM and Arts and Humanities (Regular mode)									
Programe	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
B.A.	103	108	115	118	118	121	124	126	127
M.A.	117	124	147	154	165	169	173	180	190

B.Ed	165	169	180	188	197	203	200	207	215
B.Sc.	94	92	95	93	93	94	100	106	113
M.Sc.	113	123	138	147	157	167	171	174	180
B.C.A	54	61	75	75	76	75	73	70	73
B.Sc. (Nursing)	546	527	523	462	445	384	379	358	385
B.Pharm.	74	73	82	85	85	83	82	79	93
M.B.B.S.	86	86	93	95	97	99	101	106	110
B.Tech	40	38	39	39	38	39	38	40	42
M.Tech	52	55	61	64	64	67	55	54	63

(source: AISHE 2015-16, 2018-19, 2020-21)

Analysis of above data for academic session 2011-12 to 2020-21 reveals that female outnumbered the male students in B.A. and M.A. courses remarkably in past years and recently it is almost double in M.A. course. In B.Sc. and M.Sc. courses almost same trend is observed. So we can say that in traditional courses of science female are outnumbered male in M.Sc. course. Same is true for Professional course of B.Ed. where women representation is increasing in last 10 years continuously and it goes 100: 215 in year 2020-21. While we analysed the data for B.Sc. (Nursing) it can be observed that in the starting of last decade ; in year 2011-12 the female students enrolment were more than five time per 100 male which may reduce to approximately four times in year 2019-20. Same time we also found that enrolment of female students has increasing in B.Sc. and M.Sc. especially in life science courses so we can say that female choice in nursing may shift towards professional life sciences course like biotechnology, microbiology etc. It confirmed the societal stereotype that teaching and nursing are the most suitable professions for the women. In B. Pharm and M.B.B.S courses we may saw gender gap are going to narrow down in past successive years. Same is also true for B.C.A. but still there is good gap in this course. In field of engineering and technology a wide gap is observed even it also follow the decreasing trend for last ten years sessions.

The picture at a glance looks quite satisfactory but gender is not a sole factor to decide the educational aspiration of female students. Socio-economic class, caste and cultural background also influences the educational accessibility and quality of STEM education. It is chronically thrive in our culture consciously or unconsciously. There are 3 themes that lead to gender gap in STEM as observed by Hill et al., (2012). The first one believed that men are innately superior and better than women, the second theme was women lacks interest in STEM and the third theme was based on the balance between personal and professional life.

ANALYSIS REASONS FOR GENDER GAP IN STEM EDUCATION IN INDIAN CONTEXT

In Indian society, six barriers, namely Physical, Economic, Social, Psychological, Educational Environment and masculine culture of science that restricts the success of women in STEM and increase the gender gap (Ghosh, 2012). Many other prevalent factors can foster the gender gap in STEM in Indian context that can be categorised as:

CASTE AND CLASS OF THE GIRL

The caste, class and gender altogether determine the educational and life chances of a child. The gender is one of the major sources of inequality in Indian society as it intersects the class and caste also. For example the girl belong to upper caste may have less deprivation as compare to SC/ST girls as well as boys of lower caste. Similarly, the girl from upper middle class deprivation may be less to the low-income category of boys or girls. Therefore, the gender-gap in Indian society should be view in overlapping dimension of caste and gender as well as in terms of class and gender also. According to data from All India Survey on Higher Education, (AISHE, 2011-12) the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher education in India is 20.4 for 18-23 age group. This data is comprised of 21.6 male and 18.9 for female population. Gender Parity Index (GPI) of GER for the country has come out to be 0.88. The report further reveals that SC student enrolment is 12.5% of the total student enrolment whereas students belonging to ST category constitute only 4.2% whereas 31.7% of the total students belong to OBC. This data evident that all three groups together was 48.4 even less than half as compare to one single group. Unfortunately exact data of census 2011 are not announced caste wise by Government of India (GOI) but some other sources shows that total population of upper caste is only about 30%, OBC is near about 41% , approximately 20% are SC and 10% belong to ST category. Data suggests that students enrolled in higher education shows wide caste wise gap that in turn effect enrolment of female students in their respective caste category. These data shows wide gap in higher education caste wise that in turn effect enrolment of female students in their respective caste category. Therefore, it can be deduced here that wide gender gap exist in higher education in India that intersects at class, caste and locality also. Thus, only analysing the gender gap in STEM education is not sufficient. It should be analysed in social and cultural context. Gender gap in all type of education and STEM in particular also intersect with other social variables of caste and class. Under these assumptions, we can say that the girl from upper middle class deprivation is less in term of low-income category of boys or girls. In same manner SC/ST girl of rural area more deprived than SC/ST girl from urban area. The data from the 2005 India Human Development Survey (IHDS), also shows that social background factors, access to learning resources, time devoted to formal learning activities, and cultural attitudes regarding the education of girls may contribute to ongoing gender gaps in learning. Children belongs to low SES are mostly schools drop out, or quit school. In fact, according to 2007 data collected by the National Centre for Education Statistics, low-SES children had a nearly 17% dropout rate compared to high-SES families at around 3%. These statistical figures show gender inequality in higher education is not going to fill soon, since this data includes good number of girls coming economical sound family.

STEREOTYPE BELIEFS OF PARENTS, TEACHER AND SOCIETY

Even in 21st century in most of families in Indian society celebrated the birth of a son and the birth of a daughter is filled them with worries and pain. Traditionally girls are treated as “Parayadhan” and most of parents think is just waste of money on the education of these because of her migratory nature. So, parent attitude is not much favourable for girls’ education, this attitude is became more rigid as we move towards rural areas and lower social categories. From the analysis of data regarding enrolment of girls in higher education we found that, percentage of enrolment of girls in Arts stream is quite high. This may be because most of parents want graduation degree for their daughters to make her profile striking for matrimonial purpose. It was found that support of father is very important factor in choice of STEM discipline and related career (Adya and Kaiser, 2005). Meanwhile, fee structure of STEM subjects are comparatively high and sometime extra coaching and tuition is also required for these subjects that imposing extra burden on parent pockets may cause

indifference attitude of parents to educate their daughters in STEM as compare to arts stream where, fee is very much lesser. The social class and locale are also influential factors to shape the parental attitude towards education of their daughter.

Sadker and Sadker, (1994) observed that that girls in the same classroom, reading the same text book, listening the same teacher get science education different from boys. Science textbooks and Science teachers, like others, are not free from gender bias. Science teachers too carry the same gender stereotypes as others (NCF-2005). The studies conducted on different Indian schools reported that science teachers followed discriminatory practices to teach boys and girls they encourage, pay more attention and helping hands to boys in comparison to girls. Even female teacher have also gender-biased attitude towards girl's education. Their expectations also differ on gender basis. They expect more challenging task from male in comparison to female students (Kushwaha, 2014).

INSA, (2004) also reported that societal mindsets, pressures, determine the ultimate preference and educational path of women. It also perceived that the parents of high social status and of urban area promoted their daughter to study Science subjects in which most of them wishes to see her as a doctor. They promote their daughters to study Biological rather than Physical Sciences, Mathematics and related subjects. While the parents from middle class who cannot afford the high coaching classes' fee of their both children i.e; boys and girls. So, they enforce her daughter to choose art stream subjects. They educate their boys in science subjects at the expense of their own girls. Even the science graduate and postgraduate girls are not encouraged to do Ph.D. in Science. Most of them encouraged to do B.Ed. so, that they can easily get teaching job in school the most suitable job for women because being a schoolteacher she can manage the family and home responsibilities relatively easily to other career in STEM. Therefore, in B.Ed. course women enrolment is generally higher than male.

AVAILABILITY OF STEM INSTITUTIONS

Lack of sufficient number of institutes is also major cause of low representation in STEM. Most of locally available colleges not offered undergraduate programme in science due to safety issues parents has not willing them to sent far places. High tuition fee of STEM institution, transport and hostel fee also discourage the girl's family and limit the access of girl to STEM.

LIMITED RESOURCES

Although girl's enrolment at school level is continuously, enhancing and they generally outperformed in board examination to that boys. However, when we deeply examine the gender unequal in STEM education we found that girls have limited accessibility for STEM. Since, most of girl's school or girl's college do not have course of Science due to unavailability of laboratories and other infrastructure. It limits the entry of girl in STEM world.

LACK OF ROLE MODELS

Women scientists are not famous figured in Indian culture. Even when we ask a child to tell name of five Indian scientist most of time there answer includes the name of all men scientist. Due lack of role models in Science girls are not attracted towards Science and Science is unwelcoming to them (Howes, 2002).

CONCLUSIONS

STEM education is very crucial in this 21st century for development of any nation as well as empowerment of women also. Traditionally STEM has tagged as masculine in most of societies and this notion is ubiquitous in Indian culture. As, a result a wide gender gap in

STEM education has been observed in our society. Stereotypic attitude of parent and teacher are not encouraging to study STEM and chose career in STEM. Therefore, measures should be taken to motivate the parents for encouraging their daughters to study STEM and pursue careers in it. Gender gap in STEM education is overlapped in relation to caste and class. This issues can be taken into consideration by policy makers and appropriate measure should be use to bridge the gender gap in STEM education by enhancing participation of all girls in STEM education besides her caste, class or locality.

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